

Continuous Fiber Composites Made Using an Acoustic Technique to Coat Multifilament Fiber Tows Uniformly with Metal Powders

V.R. Yallapragada, Huizhong Wang, and T.R. Bieler

Department of Materials Science and Mechanics

Michigan State University, East Lansing, MI 48824-1226, USA

ABSTRACT

A novel method of producing continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites has been developed using a powder metallurgy route. Carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composites are fabricated by coating fibers tows with aluminum powder by using acoustic energy. Fibers are precoated with a polymer (binder) to hold the metal powder onto the fiber, however, the process can also be carried out without a binder. Consolidation of the composite prepregs has been demonstrated using vacuum hot pressing. Physical properties such as fiber volume fraction, density, and coefficient of thermal expansion have been measured. Mechanical properties such as flexural strength and modulus have been measured and correlated with microstructures. Composites fabricated with this technique have homogeneous fiber distribution and minimal interface reaction products. The fracture surface indicates that the bonding between matrix and the fiber is satisfactory. Mechanical properties are 60-80% of the rule of mixture (ROM) values. Microstructure analysis of the composite has been carried out and correlated with property variations.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites are characterized by their high strength, high stiffness, elevated temperature performance and wear resistance. Especially, aluminum composites are lighter, stronger, stiffer, and offer better wear resistance, higher operating temperature, and improved dimensional stability, compared to unreinforced aluminum alloys [1]. Unfortunately, very limited literature is available on continuous carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composites made using powder metallurgy. Most of the research was concentrated on carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composites fabricated through liquid infiltration technique. Blankenburgs [2] and Ramakrishnan P. et al. [3, 4] worked on carbon fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites fabricated through powder metallurgy route.

The existing fabrication methods of continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites face many problems such as poor wetting, excessive interfacial reaction, uneven fiber distribution, and high cost of fabrication. If the fiber was wetted by the matrix material, liquid infiltration could be the first choice because of its simplicity and continuity. If the fiber was not wetted by the matrix material, a suitable fiber coating or matrix alloy addition had to be chosen. In this case, the interfacial reaction was hard to control due to over

exposure to molten metal. Other methods such as electroplating, spraying, chemical vapor deposition (CVD), and physical vapor deposition (PVD), could be suitable to get good quality composites, but they are time consuming and expensive.

Of all the approaches developed for the processing of metal matrix composites, those based on powder metallurgy processing offer great flexibility in the selection and assembly of constituents. Powder metal processing eliminates or reduces the interface reaction problems. The metal is sintered around the fiber in the solid state, a condition where the kinetics are much slower. Densification maps are useful in determining the conditions required for complete consolidation [5]. The problems associated with powder metallurgy are fiber damage may occur while applying pressure for consolidation [6], and high volume fractions are not possible if large or agglomerated powder particles present, since they cause the fibers to bunch up [7]. Alternatively, fibers are manually arranged between layers of foils and hot pressed. There are limited number of foil compositions available and the volume fraction fibers is often small, and the fiber diameters are large [8].

A new technique based on powder metallurgy route has been developed to produce continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites. The new technique has been investigated with carbon/aluminum system. This technique has potential for continuous processing of simple geometries. The technique described below is based on the continuous fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites developed by S. R. Iyer and L. T. Drzal [9].

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

PAN based AS-4 fibers with 8 μm diameter and 99.7% pure aluminum powder have been used to make the preforms. The properties of the materials used are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Properties of the materials used.

Properties	Al	Fibers	Nylon
Average particle size/Diameter (μm)	5.5	8	10.0
Density (gm/cm^3)	2.69	1.8	1.02
Surface Tension (mJ/m^2)			30.0
Melting Point ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	660		175
Tensile Strength (MPa)	82.8	3100	
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	69.0	220	
Chemical Composition			
Aluminum	99.7%		
Iron	0.18%		
Silicon	0.2%		
Source	Valimet Inc.	Hercules Inc.	

Production of Precursors Using a Binder

The unsized carbon fiber tows were made to pass through different chambers (Figure 1) to coat the fiber surface with a polymer (Nylon) which acts as binder. Then the fibers

were introduced into a fluidized bed of electrostatically charged polymer particles that were attracted to the fiber surface. After coating with polymer particles, the fibers were made to pass through an oven chamber for about 15 seconds and heated to 165 °C-170 °C for sintering to occur between adjacent particles to form globules of nylon.

Then the polymer prepreg tapes were cut into 5 cm pieces and suspended inside another chamber (aerosolizer in Figure 2) where they were coated with fine metal powder (matrix material). The primary problem in the production of carbon fiber reinforced aluminum powders is prevention of explosion. Aluminum powder can be safely handled in air as long as no ignition source is present. Thus the experiments were conducted in a dry argon atmosphere. Argon adsorbs onto the surface of aluminum powder and it will remain adsorbed for a couple of days when re-exposed to air [10].

Fig 1. Experimental set up to coat fibers with polymer.

Fig 2. Aerosolizer to coat the fibers with aluminum powder.

Figure 3 (a) shows the carbon fiber/nylon precursors with aluminum particles attached to the fiber surface. Figure 3 (b) shows the distribution of fibers in the aluminum matrix. The distribution is not always uniform and some areas have a high density of fibers and others have a low density. There are also some fiber clusters (fiber-to-fiber contact).

(a)

(b)

Fig 3. a) SEM micrograph showing aluminum powder attached to precoated carbon fibers (precoating done at 170 °C). b) Optical micrograph showing the distribution of fibers in the matrix (precoated fibers).

Consolidation of Precursors

The precursors were then stacked up and consolidated by vacuum (10^{-5} torr) hot pressing. The binder was removed before vacuum hot pressing by heating up to 300 °C for 30 minutes. A pressure of 30 MPa, temperature of 575 °C and time of 2700 seconds were the hot pressing parameters chosen.

Production of Precursors Without Binder

CFRMMC's were also made by not using any polymer binder. This was possible since metal powders form oxide coatings that can hold a static charge strong enough to attract the metal powder particles to the fiber and hold them long enough to be consolidated.

Bare carbon tows were suspended in the aerosolizing chamber and evenly coated with aluminum powder particles (Figure 2). Subsequently, sections of bare tows coated in this way were laid up in a stack and consolidated in the conventional way by vacuum hot

pressing. Some layers that had lesser amounts of powder had additional powder sprinkled on top of the layer.

The distribution of carbon fibers in the aluminum matrix is shown in Figure 4. This composite has very evenly spaced fibers with less than 2% of the fibers being in contact with each other in any particular cross section investigated.

Fig 4. Optical micrograph showing the distribution of fibers in the matrix (no precoating of fibers).

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Physical & Mechanical Property Measurements

The density and coefficient of linear thermal expansion ' α ' have been measured (Figure 5) for the composites fabricated by using bare (no binder) carbon fibers. ' α ' was measured using a Dilatometer and Archimedes principle was used to measure the density. 3 point bending tests were done on composites made using precoated (with binder) as wells as bare carbon fibers (no binder) by using a Universal Testing System (UTS). Results are given in Table 2. For bending tests, the consolidated sample (30mm \times 12mm \times 3mm) was cut into 30mm \times 2mm \times 0.5mm specimens after the composite was trimmed to eliminate unconsolidated material at the edges.

The ' α ' value determined from the dilatometer experiments is $1.8 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the temperature range of 25 to 270 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 5), where the slope ($\Delta\epsilon/\Delta T$) was determined from a linear regression. The density of the material is 2.28 gm/cm 3 . The fiber volume fraction was measured by counting the fibers on a composite cross section and it varies between 40 - 50% and based on this volume fraction, the porosity of the material is found to be less than 1%.

Table 2. Results of the room temperature 3 point bending test of the composites made using precoated carbon fibers.

Fibers	Precoated	Precoated	Bare	Bare
Specimen	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 1	Sample 2
Yield Load (lb)	0.02	0.12	N/A	N/A
Peak load (lb)	5.4	5.8	4.7	4.6
Yield Stress (psi)	170.1	101.1	N/A	N/A
Flexural Strength (psi)	49775	47622	91324	63697
(MPa)	343	328	629.0	439.0
Fiber Fraction (%)	50	50	40	40
%ROM Strength	13.0	13.0	49.0	34.0
Flexural Modulus (Ksi)	17625	13554	14742.0	12691.0
(GPa)	122.0	94.0	101.7	87.5
%ROM Modulus	80.0	62.0	78.6	67.6
Strain Failure (%)	0.65	0.55	0.66	N/A
Tensile Strength (MPa) [3] 90 MPa, 600 °C, 900 sec. 16%V _f	178			
%ROM Tensile Strength [3]	27.7			

Fig 5. Measurement of coefficient of linear thermal expansion α (25-270 °C).

Fractography

Figure 6 (a) and (b) show the SEM micrographs of the fractured surface of bend (3 point bend test) specimens. These fractographs show the even distribution of fibers with a very few fibers in contact with each other. From these fractographs, it is obvious that the fiber-matrix interface is smooth with no apparent discontinuity in the interface, even at higher magnifications. This implies that the fiber-matrix bonding is good with minimal interface reaction and no fiber damage. The fractographs show cup & cone mode of failure in the matrix and brittle failure in the fibers. These micrographs show less than 2% of the fibers being in contact with each other in any particular cross section investigated. In addition,

some fiber pull out on the order of fiber diameter is observed in the fracture surface of bend (3 point bending) specimen.

(a)

(b)

Fig 6: a) Fractograph of the 3 point bend test specimen, b) Fractograph showing ductile failure in aluminum matrix and brittle failure in carbon fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

A powder metallurgy route has been successfully utilized for the production of carbon-aluminum preregs. The preregs can be produced with or without precoating the fibers with a polymer (binder). Consolidation of the composite preregs has been demonstrated using vacuum hot pressing. Homogeneous carbon fiber distribution in aluminum matrix has been achieved. Mechanical properties are 60-80% of rule of mixture values. The SEM fractographs prove that the fiber-matrix bonding is good.

This technique can be extended to other systems of fibers and metals, intermetallics, and ceramics. The low density, low coefficient of linear thermal expansion, and high thermal conductivity makes this material suitable for thermal management applications in aerospace and electronic packaging industries where the heat generated by the components has to be dissipated, and applications where both high stiffness and high dimensional stability are required.

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